

PECULIARITIES OF ORGANIZATION AND MANAGEMENT OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract: Since the 80s of the 20th century, strategic goal setting has become the subject of pedagogical scientific research. The priority of the human factor, individual approaches to teaching and learning put on the agenda the need to study the strategic goal.

The study of the problem of goal-setting in pedagogical science covers several areas, that is, the general goals of education, as well as the clarification of educational and educational goals.

Key words: strategic, person, teacher, student, educator, leader, education, training, goal, problem, activity.

One of the most important areas of problem research is the identification of criteria that determine the effectiveness of a targeted approach to the management of general secondary schools (hereinafter - GSS). It is extremely important to determine the content of educational goals in the current situation, where serious attention is paid to increasing the effectiveness of social education.

There are different approaches to expressing the concept of "goal" in pedagogy. They differ from each other in that they approach the expression of this concept from a didactic and educational point of view.

According to a group of scientists, although educational goals are achieved using common methods, they differ in their content. Educational goals reflect the educational process in its essence. In this way, students acquire knowledge, develop the skills and abilities to use it, that is, qualitative changes occur. Educational goals determine the uniqueness of the qualities formed in a person as a result of his education.

The main result of educational goals is the formation of a person's relationship to the environment, himself and subjects. Educational goals are interrelated and interrelated and do not require any debate [4].

The analysis of historical, modern, national and foreign research, which is illuminated according to the principle of chronological problem, is considered a priority task when defining a strategic goal. Another task is to correctly

understand the impact of the analyzed studies on the activity of the head of the educational institution, in particular, on the activity of setting goals.

In order to solve certain educational issues, the manager (leader) should, first of all, organize their order and choose pedagogical tools. Here, it is important not to list, but to define a set of tools and their interrelationships. The means must be able to guarantee the achievement of the goal.

Appropriate selection of tools is the basis of the education system. It is easier for the teacher (educator) to use the tools selected according to the purpose in the educational process. Determining the set of educational tools in a changing situation is considered a simple method of internal control of an educational institution.

The personality model as a social standard of education is recognized by one group of pedagogic scientists as a "weapon", "criterion", and by representatives of another group as "alternatives" ("multiplicity"). In our opinion, the model is a continuum-based process with an ideal goal as its outcome.

Different goals require different criteria, so a single tool cannot be universal and suitable for all life situations, checking different goals. The large number of spiritual and moral qualities that must be reflected in a person requires the generalization of their dimensions from a pedagogical point of view. However, spiritual and moral qualities, including knowledge, hard work, responsibility, aesthetic culture, worldview, and physical development, cannot be measured and evaluated by a single criterion.

When it comes to the formation of a person, the ability of private pedagogical production, including the head of an educational institution and a pedagogue, is noticeable. In our opinion, these are undoubtedly important goals that represent the comprehensive development of a person. At this point, it is possible to put forward a controversial proposal that the estimation of the goal is the main place at all levels of personal development in an educational institution.

Accordingly, it is important to clarify the general goals reflected in the content of educational subjects, and in the process of developing educational programs, to reveal special educational and educational opportunities.

In recent years, many pedagogical studies have been conducted, on the basis of which new textbooks and methodical manuals were created on the basis

of choice and alternative, the special-subject and general-intersubject relationships of the purpose of education and training were studied. .

These goals are in two dimensions: 1) taking into account the progress of the process (study subject, program); 2) it means that it is determined based on the study of the nature of the organizational level (age period). The main attention should be focused on achieving the integrity and comprehensiveness of the goals of personal education and upbringing.

Integrity is considered a system-forming feature in goal planning. The rounding of goals means that conditions are created for identifying alternative goals. It is important to determine the leading educational tools, to determine the level of their use at different age levels in subjects.

The application of this idea to the activities of the head of the UOTM determines the following directions of goal determination: 1) taking into account the state of the institution as a system; 2) considering the unique aspects of the pedagogical team;

3) work based on a specific contingent of students; 4) work based on the teacher's professional training.

Before clarifying the essence of the goal, it is necessary to clarify the ideological significance of the concept of "goal" and its use in pedagogy. Here, the following three important aspects are taken into account:

- the goal is the ideal, subjective image of the expected prospective result in human activity;
- the goal is reflected as a result of the same activity (although it is reflected in the mind, it does not appear as an image of the result);
- the goal is the practical result and ideal image of the activity that represents all important factors, therefore, when choosing the goal, it is important that the goals of the pedagogical team and the teacher match certain conditions.

In our opinion, several levels are visible in the formation of the objectives of management of the activity of UO"TM. That is, educational goals of the pedagogical team - teacher - student - parents. Acceptance of educational goals at such levels increases the possibility of achieving the expected result.

Realization of the purpose of UOTM, interrelationship of educational goals and study motivations are researched as actual problems in the works of O.E. Lebedev.

According to the author, any pedagogical activity is directed to the formation of a specific person, and it is considered a social goal set by the society

for the team of the educational institution. This goal specifies the expected results of all activities reflected in the pedagogical criteria in the Strategic goals. One of the important aspects of the research is to determine the structural structure of educational goals. The following elements can be highlighted here:

1) use methods that allow students to move from cognitive activity to creative activity;

2) a creative approach to learning the content of the educational material.

The educational aspect of the educational process is evident in the formation of the skills of teaching students to work independently, to strive to perform cognitive tasks without the help of a teacher.

O. E. Lebedev was the first in the field of pedagogy to study the set of educational goals and their interrelationships, and as a result, founded the "chain of goals" or "tree of goals". According to him, the interrelationship of goals at one level is evident in the development of goals that grow from lesson to lesson on a specific subject and are reflected on the basis of the relationship between subjects, or specific goals are defined in the educational process. It is reflected in the content of several subjects.

Educational goals in research are divided into: main and special (separate). The main goals include: formation of general secondary education knowledge; formation of the system of skills and qualifications; forming a scientific outlook; education of spiritual and moral qualities in students; formation of work motives; formation of motives for social activity; formation of the purpose of study, activity, study subjects [5.].

In our opinion, such main goals, in turn, represent the approach to educational and spiritual-educational work, which includes the participation of the student as a subject in the targeted activity. Accordingly, educational goals can be expressed as a natural, mutual movement of general educational goals, as well as the result of education related to the content of specific subjects.

Pedagogical scientists strongly oppose the organization of actions such as artificially connecting the goals of education to the content of academic subjects and trying to realize all the goals of education in the study of each educational material. After all, this situation leads to formalism and creates many negative events in the educational process, creates favorable conditions for the formation of a morally immature person [5.].

Therefore, educational goals represent a specific system, and pedagogical criteria and concepts - knowledge, skills, competence, attitude to the environment, ideas, worldview and corresponding qualities of the student's

personality are reflected as its elements. The qualification of classification of existing objects of activity is one of the qualifications widely spread in the educational system, its formation is related to knowledge defining the task and activity system [6].

The influence of determining the content and methods of the goal on the pedagogical activity is recognized as a result of the research of the relationship between the goal and the pedagogical activity. Two-way communication should be a means of its implementation. Current pedagogical situations indicate the need to change the content of approaches to the assessment of activity results. That is, in the center of pedagogical changes, the influence of the teacher should be focused on the person who is the object of education, his needs, interests, aspirations and ideals.

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